

Energy conservation characterizes sleep in sharks

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Supplementary Material

Materials and Methods

Experimental animals and housing

Seven adult draughtboard sharks (*Cephaloscyllium isabellum*; 4 females, 3 males; 766-2705 g in weight; 350-720 mm in length) were obtained in 2018 from a commercial fisherman of the Leigh coast, northern New Zealand. At the Leigh Marine Laboratory, they were held in a 1200 L tank with flow-through 200 µm filtered seawater (hourly water changes) at ambient temperature (17-18 °C range) and fed pilchards every three days. Animals were held on a 12:12 light:dark cycle and allowed to acclimate for at least two weeks before experiments. Experiments were approved by the University of Auckland Animal Ethics committee (approval no. 001983).

Intermittent-flow respirometry setup

The custom-built respirometer held one shark at a time and consisted of a sealed acrylic chamber (external length: 870 mm, width: 320 mm, depth: 170 mm; capacity: 38 L) with tubing between it and two small submersible pumps (eHeim compact 1000, Stuttgart, Germany). The chamber was large enough to facilitate free movement and swimming of sharks. The first (circulation) pump was connected to the chamber at opposite ends and was designed to constantly mix seawater internally for accurate oxygen saturation measures. The combined

volume of the chamber, circulation pump and tubing was 42.7 L. The second (flush) pump was only connected to the chamber at one end and was designed to flush fresh, clean seawater from the main experimental tank on demand through the chamber via activation of an on/off relay unit (Cleware USB-Switch C, Hollingstedt, Germany). Seawater was flushed out of the chamber via a tube port at the opposite end. The flush outflow ran to a level above the reservoir water level to avoid any water exchange while the pump was off (Svendsen et al., 2016A). The two pumps ran in a crossflow design ensuring a high degree of mixing in the chambers when both were running (Svendsen et al., 2016A). Oxygen saturation of the water inside the chambers was measured continuously (at 1 Hz) using a sensor spot (OXSP5, Pyroscience, Aachen, Germany) placed on the inside of the chamber lid that was monitored and recorded by a FireSting O₂ meter (Pyroscience, Aachen, Germany). The O₂ meter was calibrated to air-saturated water from the experimental tank before each trial.

Oxygen consumption rate ($\dot{M}O_2$) was measured using intermittent stop-flow respirometry (Steffensen, 1989), where a respirometry cycle involved a period with the chamber 'open' to the surrounding water when the flush pump was on, and 'closed' when off. The open period is also referred to as the 'flush' phase, where metabolites are expelled, and oxygen saturation is replenished. This ensures oxygen saturation in the chambers always returned to > 92%. Following closure, oxygen saturation in the chamber declines linearly when fish respire at a constant rate, % O₂ never fell below 84% (Svendsen et al., 2016A). Oxygen measured by the sensor spots, however, is delayed behind chamber average and the recorded change in oxygen saturation is initially concave down in the closed phase. Closed periods were thus split into a short 'wait' and 'measurement' phase with oxygen saturation data only gathered from the latter when the decline was linear. Respirometry cycle (measure, flush, wait) lengths varied between individual sharks, and day and night due to variations in mass and

activity levels, respectively, with the following ranges: measure day 600-1200 s, night 420-780 s; flush: day and night 240-300 s; wait: day and night 180 s.

The FireSting O₂ meter was connected to a laptop computer with customized respirometry software (LeighResp, John Atkins design) that automated the respirometer cycle and logged oxygen saturation and calculated the change of oxygen saturation decrease per unit time ($\frac{\Delta\%sat}{\Delta t}$) for each measurement phase. $\dot{M}O_2$ in units of milligrams of oxygen consumed per hour (mg O₂ h⁻¹), was then calculated using the equation:

$$\dot{M}O_2 = \frac{\Delta\%sat}{\Delta t} aV_{RE}$$

where, a is the solubility coefficient of oxygen (mg O₂ %sat⁻¹ L⁻¹) in seawater (35 ppt salinity, 17.5°C temperature, ~100 kPa atmospheric pressure; Loligo Systems, Viborg, Denmark) and V_{RE} is the effective volume of the respirometry chamber (L, chamber minus shark volume estimated as body mass assuming equal density as seawater).

Video recording setup

Video recordings of animal behaviour during the 24-h measurement period were achieved following the methods detailed in Kelly et al. (2020). Two further IR-sensitive cameras, fitted with custom-built waterproof housings, were submerged within the reservoir tank and placed centrally along the left and right (long) sides of the respirometry chamber (placed 400 mm back from the chamber), in order to record shark lateral posturing and eye states.

Experimental protocol

All trials were carried out in a respirometer held in a larger 1500 L experimental tank (1900 mm diameter, 600 mm depth) supplied continuously with flow-through 1 μm filtered, UV treated (ClearTec UV-C 11W, Pond One, Australia) seawater at 17.5 °C. Animals were individually placed into the sealed respirometry chamber 24 h after last feeding. Automated, intermittent-flow respirometry and video recordings began 48 h later to allow each animal to acclimate to their new conditions and reach a post absorptive state before data collection began. Each protocol then lasted 24 h under a 12:12 light:dark photoperiod regime. Three respirometry cycles were run after each shark was removed to measure background changes in O_2 (Svendsen et al., 2016A), but these levels were found to be negligible (slopes non-significantly different from zero, $p > 0.05$). Body mass recordings of sharks were taken before and after each protocol via a digital bench scale (Wedderburn WS20110K, Auckland, New Zealand). The respirometry chamber was scrubbed with dilute sodium hypochlorite then thoroughly rinsed with fresh water following the end of each experimental protocol.

Data analysis

Custom-written software calculated the gradient of the % O_2 decline and the associated residual sum of squares (R^2). $\dot{\text{M}}\text{O}_2$ was then calculated from the decline in oxygen saturation as described above. All metabolic analyses were carried out on residual values from regressions of $\dot{\text{M}}\text{O}_2$ against body mass (Packard and Boardman, 1988, 1999; Lesku et al., 2009). The first metabolic analysis compared rates during day and night. We regressed the mean day and night $\dot{\text{M}}\text{O}_2$ for each shark against body mass (regression I) and then used a paired Student's t-test on the residuals (accounting for repeated measures) to compare day versus night. We visualized this with residuals of all $\dot{\text{M}}\text{O}_2$ values calculated with respect to regression I (Figure 1b). Secondly, we compared differences in residual $\dot{\text{M}}\text{O}_2$ between activity states (irrespective of

photoperiod) (Figure S1). As bouts of each activity state varied greatly in length and R^2 within each measure period, we subsampled data points from all measure periods and applied strict criteria in order to standardize the quality of the data while retaining a large sample size. Each data point met the criteria of an $R^2 > 0.80$ and a length of > 90 s (in order to clean the data of false $\dot{M}O_2$ values due to the inherent variability in the measurement of O_2 saturation; 631 of 1452 cycles retained). We recognize that metabolic data with an $R^2 > 0.95$ is typically considered the most reliable (Svendsen et al., 2016A; 2016B). When we applied a criteria of $R^2 > 0.95$ to our subsampling method, we obtained data that was qualitatively similar to that which we obtained with an $R^2 > 0.80$. Importantly, however, the $R^2 > 0.80$ data included a much larger sample size which was more amenable to statistical analysis. Similarly, the time criteria of > 90 s maximized sample size (increased with decreasing critical value) while maintaining quality in $\dot{M}O_2$ values (increased with increasing critical value). We, therefore, regressed the mean swimming, rest and sleep $\dot{M}O_2$ for each shark against body mass (regression II). The residuals were then used to compare the three activity states with a mixed effects model (individual as random effect; activity as a fixed effect). We conducted Tukey's *post hoc* tests to determine where significance was reached. We visualized this with residuals of all $\dot{M}O_2$ values calculated with respect to regression II (Figure 1c). Thirdly, activity $\dot{M}O_2$ data was further partitioned by photoperiod. Not all combinations of activity and photoperiod were included as no sharks engaged in swimming during the day with $\dot{M}O_2$ values that met selection criteria. We, therefore, regressed the mean $\dot{M}O_2$ values from the five combinations (night/swimming, day/rest, night/rest, day/sleep, night/sleep) for each shark against body mass (regression III). We used a mixed effects model (individual as a random effect; activity and photoperiod as fixed effects) to determine whether there was a significant difference in residual $\dot{M}O_2$ across the activity and photoperiod combinations. Tukey's *post hoc* tests again determined where significance was reached. We visualized this with residuals of all $\dot{M}O_2$

values calculated with respect to regression III (Figure 1d). A mixed effects model (individual as random effect; activity and activity length as fixed effects) was used to distinguish whether rest and sleep duration affected rest and sleeping residual $\dot{M}O_2$ values calculated from regression III. All rest and sleeping residual $\dot{M}O_2$ values were used in this analysis and needed cube-root transformation to satisfy the normality assumption of the model. We visualized these data with a scatter-plot of back-transformed residual $\dot{M}O_2$ values (Figure 1e). Generalized linear mixed effects models with binomial distribution, in which individual was set as random effect, were used to compare differences in posture and eye state between activity states and photoperiods (Figure 2a-d). Finally, respirometry cycles were subsampled according to posture (flat, upright, swimming) and the same criteria as above was applied to clean the data (612 of 1393 cycles retained). As day/swimming was, again, not represented by any $\dot{M}O_2$ values, we regressed the mean $\dot{M}O_2$ values from the five represented posture/photoperiod combinations for each shark against body mass (regression IV). To obtain a normal distribution of residuals, a log10-log10 transformation was needed for regression IV. We also combined the five available crosses of posture and photoperiod to form a single variable (levels of night/swimming, day/upright, night/upright, day/flat, night/flat) to perform a mixed effects model (individual as a random effect; posture and photoperiod as fixed effects) on the residual $\dot{M}O_2$ values. Again, Tukey's *post hoc* tests determined where significance was reached. To calculate residuals of $\dot{M}O_2$ values for visualization, values were firstly back-transformed (Figure 2e). All analyses were conducted in R (v 1.0.143), using lme4 package for mixed effects models.

Figure S1. Time series of $\dot{M}O_2$ levels across three activity states (blue indicates sleep; grey denotes rest; red reflects swimming) using subsampled data points from intermittent-flow respirometry for a single shark over a 24-h period (L:D 12:12). Only values that satisfied applied criteria of an $R^2 > 0.80$ and a length of > 90 s were used.

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